

**IPHONE OPERATIONAL IN THE SYSTEM MOBILE APPLICATIONS
TO CREATE INTENDED PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENTS****Akhmedova Zulhumor Ikromovna**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10517228>**INTRODUCTION**

As a result of the transition of the higher education system of our country to the credit-module system, great changes have been made in this system. Decree No. PF-5953 dated March 2, 2020 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions " 2020/2021 academic year It is said that the procedure for gradually transferring the educational process to the credit-module system should be introduced in higher educational institutions of the republic starting from 2016. In this system, the percentage of hours allocated to independent work of students has been increased.

Based on this, in order to improve the quality of the educational system in higher education institutions, it is necessary to create and use modern information and communication technologies along with traditional teaching tools. To solve this problem, it will be necessary to develop software tools intended for teaching, including electronic teaching-methodical complexes.

Mobile application platform for monitoring republican educational centers dedicated to creating. The mobile application platform is considered a type of methodological support of the non-governmental educational process, which includes all components of the organization of non-governmental educational process activities.

iPhone operational in the system mobile applications to create intended programming environments

The Xcode programming environment is the first programming environment offered by Apple to create software tools for the Macintosh operating system. As a result of the development of technology, software products for the following devices are created today using the Xcode programming environment:

1. MacBook ;
2. MacBook Air ;
3. MacBook Pro ;
4. iPod ;

- 5. iPad ;
- 6. iPad Pro ;
- 7. iPhone ;
- 8. watchOS ;
- 9. tvOS ;

The Xcode programming environment has the following interface :

the Create a new Xcode project command is selected from the resulting window, or you can create a new project using the New -> Project command from the File menu.

After selecting the Create a new Xcode project command, the iOS section is activated from the resulting dialog. Using the iOS section, it is possible to create an application for devices running on the basis of the iOS operating system. From the iOS section, the Single View Application command is activated. This command creates an empty project. After that, the name of the project and the storage address will be specified, and a new project will be created and have the following interface:

The project contains the following standard files:

1. AppDelegate.h and AppDelegate.m files - these files are a set of necessary files for configuring parameters during the program startup;
2. ViewController.h and ViewController.m files are the main controls of the program, and the program tasks are displayed in these files, that is, the program code is written. In the ViewController.h file, the developer declares the variables that are applied or used when building the application. How to declare variables:

a) `{ NSInteger <variable_name>;
CGFloat < variable_name >;
NSString < variable_name >;
..... }`

The main purpose of declaring variables in this order is to grant access only to the current controller.

b) `@property (nonatomic, strong) NSInteger < variable_name >;
@property (nonatomic, strong) CGFloat < variable_name >;
@property (nonatomic, strong) NSString < variable_name >;`

The main purpose of declaring variables in this order is to allow those variables to be accessed from within the optional controller.

The ViewController.m file contains program codes written by the programmer, that is, functions and methods are reflected in this controller.

The Swift programming language is the programming language included in the Xcode development environment. This programming language has been

developed by Apple since 2014 and is based on Objective-C, C and C++ programming languages.

The Swift programming language has the following default data types:

1. Int is an integer structure. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
2. Int8 is an integer structure. Takes up 1 byte of memory;
3. Int16 is an integer structure. Takes up 2 bytes of memory;
4. Int32 is an integer structure. Takes up 4 bytes of memory;
5. Int64 is an integer structure. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
6. NSInteger is a structure of integers. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
7. A float is a real number structure. Takes up 4 bytes of memory;
8. Double is a structure of real numbers. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
9. CGFloat is a structure of real numbers. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
10. String is a string data structure. Occupies 24 bytes of memory;
11. NSString is a string data structure. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
12. Character is a string data structure. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
13. UIColor is a data type for working with colors. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
14. NSData is a data type designed to represent all of the above types through a special data type. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
15. NSURL is a data type designed to work with url data. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;
16. NSObject is the data type used to create an object of the class. Takes up 8 bytes of memory;

To find out the memory size of standard data types, it is enough to enter the following program code:

```
print(MemoryLayout<data_type>.size)
```

```
For example: override func viewDidLoad() {  
super.viewDidLoad()  
print(MemoryLayout<Int>.size)  
}
```

Here, the override func viewDidLoad() function is the default method of the UIViewController class. This function is used before starting the optional window of the mobile device. And the print command is used to print data. The result of the above program code fragment is completed by printing the number 8.

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